

Pyrimidines. Part X: Synthesis of Some *Bis*(Aryloxy) Pyrimidines*

D. SEN and P. K. DUTTA

Department of Applied Chemistry, University Colleges of Science and Technology, Calcutta University, Calcutta-9

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Synthesis of some 2, 4-*bis*(aryloxy)-6-aminopyrimidines and isomeric 2-amino-4, 6-*bis*(aryloxy)pyrimidines are described.

It has been shown that many pyrimidines having two aryloxy groups at 2 and 4 positions exhibit herbicidal¹ and antimicrobial² activities. Many other pyrimidines having a combination of aryloxy and amino (or substituted amino) groups have also been found to possess antimalarial³⁻⁴ and antifolic⁵ activities. It therefore appears likely that 2,4-*bis*(aryloxy)-6-aminopyrimidines (I) and isomeric compounds (II) will exhibit interesting biological properties.

Synthesis of some new compounds of type I and II is being reported in the present paper.

- Ia, OR = *p*-methylphenoxy
Ib, = *m*-methylphenoxy
Ic, = *p*-methoxyphenoxy
Id, = *p*-chlorophenoxy
IIa, OR = phenoxy
IIb, = *p*-methylphenoxy
IIc, = *m*-methylphenoxy
IId, = *p*-methoxyphenoxy
IIe, = *p*-chlorophenoxy.

For the synthesis of the compounds we started from dihydroxy-aminopyrimidines. 2,4-dihydroxy-6-aminopyrimidine and 2-amino-4,6-dihydroxypyrimidine were reacted with phosphorus oxychloride to form 2,4-dichloro-6-aminopyrimidine⁶ and 2-amino-4,6-dichloropyrimidine⁷. These chloro compounds were then fused with four equivalents of an appropriate phenol in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate to give the title compounds. This method of synthesis is similar to that used by Matsukawa and Shirakawa⁸.

Other methods for the preparation of the *bis*(aryloxy)pyrimidines have been reported^{9,10} but these were found less suitable for our compounds.

The *bis*(aryloxy) pyrimidines synthesized are all white crystalline solids insoluble in water but sparingly soluble in alcohol. They all exhibit two strong absorption bands with maxima near 230 and 260 nm.

The spectral data and other details about the compounds are given in Table I.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes on a copper block. All melting points reported are corrected.

In crystallization the term alcohol always refers to 95% (w/w) ethanol.

Absorption spectra of the compounds were determined in absolute alcohol in 0.5 cm cell in Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer.

For analysis the compounds were dried over phosphorus pentoxide for 18 hr at 110°/1 mm.

General method for the preparation of bis(aryloxy) pyrimidines :

The dichloropyrimidine (0.00125 mole) was mixed with the phenolic compounds (0.005 mole) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.005 mole), and the mixture was heated in an oil bath at 140°-160° for 30 min. The melt was cooled to room temperature and was treated with 5% sodium hydroxide solution (30 ml.). The resulting oil was then extracted

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TABLE 1*

Compound No.	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)	Molecular formula	Analysis %		U.V. Absorption	
				Found	Calcd.	λ_{max} nm	$\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$
Ia	55	163	$C_{18}H_{17}N_3O_2$	C: 69.73 H: 5.04 N: 13.17	70.35 5.53 13.35	222 238 260	28.30 14.31 10.81
Ib	58	123	$C_{18}H_{17}N_3O_2$	C: 70.01 H: 5.54 N: 13.45	70.35 5.53 13.35	230 260	44.36 33.31
Ic	41	126	$C_{18}H_{17}N_3O_4$	C: 64.10 H: 5.19 N: 11.45	63.71 5.01 12.39	230 260	30.77 13.07
Id	74	173	$C_{16}H_{11}N_3Cl_2O_2$	C: 54.66 H: 3.21 N: 11.05	55.17 3.16 12.07	230 250	41.90 8.35
IIa	62	158	$C_{18}H_{13}N_3O_2$	C: 68.75 H: 4.95 N: 15.36	68.81 4.66 15.05	234 270	48.54 48.26
IIb	53	143	$C_{18}H_{17}N_3O_2$	C: 70.78 H: 5.76 N: 13.54	70.35 5.53 13.35	222 250 260	48.35 36.11 32.65
IIc	74	145	$C_{18}H_{17}N_3O_2$	C: 69.49 H: 5.94 N: 13.65	70.35 5.53 13.35	216 262	26.32 10.30
IId	58	192-193	$C_{18}H_{17}N_3O_4$	C: 63.73 H: 5.15 N: 12.30	63.71 5.01 12.39	230 270	46.52 13.36
IIe	77	189	$C_{18}H_{11}N_3Cl_2O_2$	C: 55.78 H: 3.27 N: 11.82	55.17 3.16 12.07	230 270	43.50 16.31

* Ia, Ib, Ic and Id were crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether (60°-80°) mixture, compound IIb, IIc, IId and IIe from alcohol and compound IIa from alcohol-water mixture.

with benzene (2 × 25 ml.). The benzene solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and treated with decolorising carbon and filtered. On evaporation of benzene, the product was obtained as a solid and was purified by crystallization.

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